

A STUDY OF EMPLOYEE RETENTION

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Abstract:

Employee retention plays an important role in an organization because it affects employee performance. The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of employee retention strategies namely employee reward programs, flexible working hours, timely promotions, career developmental programs, performance-based bonus on employee retention and employee performance. The study results revealed that employee retention strategies have positive effect on employee retention as well as employee performance. The theoretical framework of this study would encourage the companies and their employers to constitutes their employees as an important resource as they are difficult to retain and costly to acquire. The study would also helpful for researchers and academicians to understand the role of employee retention in an organization. The major purpose of this study is to identify and analyze the major determinant factors that affect employee retention. This research closely looked at the following broad factors: Health and wellness benefits, Personal Development, Compensation, Work life Balance, Top performer Recognition and Reward, superior-Subordinate Relationship, training and development, Job Characteristics and Job Commitment, Financial Rewards and Welfare Programs. A total of 615 self-administrative questionnaires data is received and the data was analyzed with the help of SPSS_v20 software. The results demonstrated that employee retention strategies have a significant role in employee retention as well as outstanding enterprise performance. The outcomes of this study will help organizations understand the importance of employee retention factors and strategies in achieving superior organizational overall performance and in retaining competent employees

Keywords: Employee reward programmes, compensation, work life balance, financial rewards, welfare programmes, job commitment.

Introduction:

Employee Retention is a process in the present scenario of high economic growth and development and rapid globalization, the fight for talent is becoming increasingly intense. Talent or human resource is a major asset for any organization. The organization invest high amount of money for their HR Practices recruitment, selection & training programmes and what happens to firm if these talents or employees leave the organization in short while pursuing new opportunities. Plagued by unpredictable retention trends and cut throat global competition, organizations are now achieving the need to understand the supply-demand equation better in order to collect efficient approaches to attract and retain top competent employees. In the best of worlds, human resources would love their works, like their co-workers, work hard for their employers, get paid well for their work, have sufficient chances for advancement, and flexible schedules so they could attend to personal or family requirements when necessary and never leave. But then there's the real world and in the real world, employees, do leave, either because they want more money, not interested about working conditions provided by company, hate their co-employees, need a change, or because their spouse gets a dream job in another state. Employee Retention is major to the long-term health and success of any organization; however, it is becoming increasingly difficult for company across the globe to attract, motivate and retain significant talent. Employee Turnover is a major challenge faced by the companies globally (James, Leena; Mathew, Lissy). Retention rates are still on the increase and as the war for talent becomes more intense each year it is becoming increasingly significant for organizations to ensure they have the right in which the human resources are encouraged to remain with the company for the maximum period of time or until the completion of the project. Employee Retention is beneficial for the company as well as the workforce.

Employee retention refers to the ability of the organization to retain its human resources and its emerging as a big challenge to companies. Organization culture, pay, remuneration, flexibility and job satisfaction highly influence the retention rate for any company. The paper gives the major factors affected to leave his job and also talks extensively about the strategies are helpful to improve the employee retention. The paper elaborates on the retention factors such as compensation, health and wellness benefits, training programmes, skills recognition, superior and subordinate relationships, career development, etc and helps in understanding the significance of effective communication and employee encouragement for the cause of employee retention.

Objectives of the study:

- To Identify the factors influencing Employee Retention.
- To study the employee retention strategies.
- To analyze how those employee retention strategies, affect employee retention.

Significance of the study:

The significance of this study lies in the gist of the IT industry in recent years, where on one hand the employee turnover has been alarmingly high, thus affecting the organization a lot. Many empirical studies have been made on various parts of the world in connection with different concepts of Human resource management, but in previous researches there exists a gap that most literature sources address the topic of retention merely by concentrating in-depth on retention factors and strategies that could be used by organizations to motivate employees. Despite of the high importance attached to the concept of Retention strategies, and the importance of retention and its factors focusing on improve retention rate in Information Technology sector. This study is an attempt to access the patterns of work place retention factors and strategies in IT and to analyse the relationship between employee retention and indicators of employee retention such as employee performance, employee commitment, employee satisfaction, employee participation and employee morale. The end result of this study will make it easier for managers to identify what motivates the employee and how the implementation of such motivational factors can lead to higher levels of employee retention accompanied by increased performance, morale and satisfaction.

Literature Review

Hytter (2007) explained that there are some factors such as personal premises of loyalty, trust, commitment, and identification and attachment with the organization have a direct influence on employee retention and workplace factors such as rewards, leadership style, career opportunities, the training and development of skills, physical working conditions, and the balance between professional and personal life have an indirect influence.

Garg & Rastogi (2006) explained that in today's competitive environment feedback is very essential for organization.

Retention Involves Five Basic Things

Environment: A motivated employee wants to contribute to work areas outside of his specific job description.

Ramlall (2003) stressed that a suitable work environment is the need of an employee in an organization as it will encourage commitment.

Nelson(2006), explained in his study that job satisfaction is priceless, incomparable and invaluable. Hopeless employees negatively upsetting the desire level of work. A little amount of employees which are satisfied with their work not only affect the performance but also the work environment affects the performance of employees and performance of organization.

Growth: Growth is an integral part of every individual's career. If an employee cannot foresee his path of career development in his current organization, there are chances that he'll leave the organization as soon as he gets an opportunity.

Grossman, J.(2002) stressed that Work growth is the effect of employee performance in the organization as well as the result of organizational provenance provided to employees by organization. The Growth and productivity is the ultimate result of employee behavior such as performance, retention, satisfaction of employees.

Compensation: Compensation constitutes the largest part of the retention process. The employees always have high expectations regarding their compensation packages. Compensation includes: Salary and Wages, Bonus, Health Insurance, after retirement benefits.

Davies, Taylor, & Savery (2001) Compensation to top workers is given by every organization but very few organizations uses it strategically. They said that "Salary and benefits policies are not being used strategically, within the organization to improve morale, reduce turnover, and achieve targets within an establishment". In a research it was concluded that although compensation was not one of the top factors influencing non management turnover but compensation can act as a critical factor in reducing managerial turnover and increasing commitment.

Relationship: Sometimes the relationship with the management and the peers become the reason for an employee to leave the organization. The management is often not able to provide an employee a supportive work culture and environment in terms of personnel and professional relationships. A supportive work culture helps grow employees professionally and boosts employee's satisfaction. There are times when an employee starts feeling bitterness towards the management or peers, which leads to less satisfaction and eventually attrition.

Armstrong (2003) Employee relations consist of all those areas of human resource management that deals with employees directly and through collective agreements where trade unions are recognised. The union practices for the welfare and good working condition of the employees. Employee relations are concerned with generally managing the relationship between employer and employees at the workplace that can be formal e.g. contract of employment or procedural agreement.

Support: Employees today are asking for a work place that helps them balance the demands of their work and family lives, rather than forcing them to one over the other. Schemes like: Special schemes for their children, Scholarship, Medical benefits, Training etc

William Kahn(1993) "The harnessing of organisation members' selves to their work roles; in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances." Employee engagement with the definition: "an employee's involvement with, commitment to, and satisfaction with work. Employee engagement is a part of employee retention."

Research methodology and Statistical tools used for Data Analysis:

After the field work the data collected from the primary and secondary sources is consolidated, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted. For the purpose of analyzing the data, statistical methods and samples are used. Mean and standard deviation was used to find out weightages and percentages on responses received. Advanced statistical tools like ANOVA test, percentage analysis, Kruskal-Wallis test and Cronbach Alpha tests are used for analyzing satisfaction levels of employees regarding employee retention.

Discussion on Pilot Study

The pilot study was mainly conducted for testing the questionnaire drafted. The objective to conduct such pilot survey is to design a structured questionnaire that will be more realistic and meaningful for the research. Pilot survey has been conducted to pre-test the questionnaire to test its reliability and validity. The output of the Pilot Survey explains how the participants gave their responses and views not only regarding the questionnaire but also about the benefits of the study that will add to the industry. A sample of 40 respondents was selected from IT companies. The survey instruments were then pretested to check for any disagreement. The collected information was statistically tested to calculate of coefficient, which validates the questionnaire is 95.1% reliable i.e., (0.951).

Analysis and Discussions:

Competent employees' retention is very critical to the long-term benefits and success of the organization. Retaining our best employee ensures product sales, customer satisfaction, contented co-workers and reporting authority, effective progression planning and deeply embedded organizational knowledge and learning: Following are some potential factors for an employee to stay long time in the organization such as work schedule flexibility, personal development, personal development ,compensation, work life balance, top performer, recognition and rewards, superior-subordinate relationship, training and career development, job characteristics and job commitment, financial rewards and welfare programmes, less compensation packages and benefits. And following are some potential factors for an employee to leave such as frequent job rotations, lack of support from superiors, lack of importance for professional growth and development, lack of support from superiors, conflicts with other employees, in equality or favouritism, ineffective organization communication, timely increments and promotions, personal reasons.

**Table.1 - Factors that make the employees to stay Long time at the organization (Ranking the factors)
Test Statistics**

	Factor	Company (N=615) Mean	Rank	df	Chi-Square Value	Asymp.Sig Value
1	Work Schedule Flexibility	3.7545	2	4	9.792	0.044
2	Health and wellness benefits	3.8602	5	4	2.859	0.582
3	Personal Development	3.8049	6	4	1.316	0.859
4	Compensation	3.7431	3	4	3.080	0.545
5	Work life Balance	3.9122	1	4	4.280	0.369
6	Top performer Recognition and Rewards	3.7626	10	4	4.183	0.382
7	Superior-Subordinate Relationship	3.8618	4	4	5.830	0.212
8	Training and Career Development	3.8683	8	4	4.898	0.298
9	Job Characteristics and Job Commitment	3.8862	9	4	4.357	0.360
10	Financial Rewards and Welfare Programmes	3.7919	7	4	3.203	0.524

a. Kruskal Wallis Test.

Results And Discussions:

As per above table 1 it has been inferred that most of the employees given highest significance (high rank) to work life balance work schedule flexibility and compensation management, and given least significant (low rank) to top performer recognition and rewards and job characteristics and commitment factors of retention.

Kruskal Wallis Test was applied. Since the calculated Chi-Square values of all retention factors that make the employees to stay long time at the organizations are less than Tabulated values and the significance value is greater than the 0.05 for all the factors. So, the ranking of employees on various retention factors that make the employees to stay long time at the organizations are not same. So that we can interpret from the analysis that the employee's feel the organization should provide and develop work schedule flexibility according to employee convenience, implement effective compensation package and benefits, giving significance of work life balance factors are helpful to improve employee satisfaction and they retain long time in the company.

Table.2 - Factors influencing the employees to Leave from the organization (Ranking the factors)

S.No	Factor	Company (N=615) Mean	Rank	df	Chi-Square Value	Asymp.Sig Value
1	Less Compensation Packages and Benefits	3.9122	1	4	0.014	0.993
2	Frequent Job Rotations	3.7546	8	4	4.457	0.108
3	Lack of support from superiors	3.7919	7	4	3.486	0.175
4	Lack of importance for professional growth and Development	3.8683	3	4	0.428	0.807
5	Lack of effective working conditions	3.8049	6	4	4.521	0.104
6	Conflicts with Other Employees	3.8602	5	4	1.222	0.543
7	In equality or Favouritism	3.8862	2	4	0.117	0.943
8	Ineffective organization communication	3.8618	9	4	4.166	0.125
9	Lack of Increments and Promotions	3.7545	4	4	2.991	0.224
10	Personal Reasons	3.7431	10	4	3.383	0.184

a. Kruskal Wallis Test.

Results and Discussions:

As per above table 2 it has been inferred that most of the employees given highest significance (high rank) to less compensation package and benefits, inequality and favoritism, Lack of importance for professional growth and Development factors of employee retention, and given least significant (low rank) to personal reasons, ineffective organization communication and frequent job rotation factors of retention.

Kruskal Wallis Test was applied. Since the calculated Chi-Square values of all retention factors that make the employees to stay long time at the organizations are less than Tabulated values and the significance value is greater than the 0.05 for all the factors. So, the ranking of employees on various retention factors that make the employees to leave from the organizations are not same. So that we can interpret from the analysis that the employee's feel the organization should design and implement effective compensation package and benefits, giving significance to equality principle and avoid favoritism, give significance for professional growth and Development factors are helpful to improve employee commitment to the company and improve employee retention.

Conclusion:

Employee retention plays an important role in an organization because it affects employee performance. The present study revealed that employee retention strategies namely employee reward programmes, flexible working hours, employee training, performance-based bonus, employee recreation, career developmental programmes have positive effect on employee retention as well as employee performance. The need for organizations to retain their talents is

crucial for their ability to remain in business depends on it. Although this study attempted to bring forth all the factors related to stay long time in the organization and factors influence to leave from organization. From the study employees given highest significant factors to stay in company are compensation, work schedule flexibility, work life balance and the factors to leave from the company are less compensation package and benefits, inequality and favoritism, Lack of importance for professional growth and Development factors of employee retention. Based on the research the organization should concentrate on these retention strategies flexible working hours, employee rewards, career development programmes so that it will increase the satisfaction level of employees which will increase employee retention.

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